

LOKATIV KOMPONENLI GAPLARNI TAHLIL QILISHDA FOYDALANILGAN
LINGVISTIK METODLAR XUSUSIDA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18340455>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillarida lokativ komponent ishtirok etgan gaplarni tahlil qilishda qo'llaniladigan lingvistik metodlar ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan yoritiladi. Tadqiqot struktur-semantik, distributiv, transformatsion, funksional va kognitiv yondashuvlar asosida olib borildi. Qiyosiy tahlil natijasida har ikki tilda lokativ komponentlarning ifodalanish vositalari, sintaktik pozitsiyasi va konseptual talqini aniqlashtirildi.

Kalit so'zlar: lokativ komponent, makon semantikasi, gap sintaksisi, lingvistik metod, qiyosiy tahlil.

Abstract: This article scientifically and theoretically covers the linguistic methods used in the analysis of sentences with a locative component in Uzbek and English. The research was conducted on the basis of structural-semantic, distributive, transformational, functional, and cognitive approaches. As a result of the comparative analysis, the means of expression, syntactic position, and conceptual interpretation of locative components in both languages were clarified.

Keywords: locative component, spatial semantics, sentence syntax, linguistic method, comparative analysis.

Аннотация: В данной статье научно и теоретически освещаются лингвистические методы, используемые при анализе предложений с участием локативного компонента в узбекском и английском языках. Исследование проводилось на основе структурно-семантического, дистрибутивного, трансформационного, функционального и когнитивного подходов. В результате сравнительного анализа были уточнены средства выражения, синтаксическая позиция и концептуальная интерпретация локативных компонентов в обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: локативный компонент, пространственная семантика, синтаксис предложения, лингвистический метод, сравнительный анализ.

Introduction. In modern linguistics, the study of the components that make up the semantic structure of a sentence is one of the important scientific problems. In particular, locative components expressing spatial relations complement the content of predicative units, ensuring the clarity and comprehensibility of speech. The category of locativity occupies an important place in the semantics of a sentence by expressing the place, direction, and point of origin of the action.

In Uzbek linguistics, locative units are mainly studied within the framework of the adverbial modifier of place, while in English this issue is studied through the system of prepositions. However, on the example of both languages, there is a need for a methodological comparative and comprehensive study of sentences with a locative component.

The purpose of this article is to identify the linguistic methods used in the analysis of sentences with a locative component and to conduct a comparative analysis of them using the example of the Uzbek and English languages.

Methods. The following linguistic methods were used in the research process:

Structural-semantic method

This method serves to determine the relationship between the syntactic structure of a sentence and its semantic content. In the Uzbek language, locative components are often expressed by case endings (-da, -ga, -dan), while in English they are expressed by prepositions (in, at, on, to, from).

In the English language, the locative instrumental sema is mainly manifested in the combination of nouns representing vehicles, body parts, with various prepositions and the depiction of space and means in the performance of an action:

1. *Meg leaned her head on her hand* (L.M. Alcott. Little Women; 45);
2. *Oliver sat by the fireplace in the small parlor* (Charles Dickens, Oliver Twist; 39);
3. *Wilbur rolled over in the dirt, enjoying the warmth of the sun* (E.B. White.

Charlotte's Web; 56);

4. *They spent time in the courtyard, enjoying the sunshine;*
5. *He saw nothing in the mirror* (J.K. Rowling. Harry Potter; 35).

In the given examples, if the purpose is to clarify the expression of locativity in the syntactic units *on her hand*, *by the fireplace*, *in the dirt*, *in the courtyard*, *in the mirror*, then they can be replaced by adverbial elements *here/there*. In determining the instrumental sema, *by means of*, *by virtue of*, *with the help of*, *with the help of*, *by dint of* can be expressed using the transformation of addition.

Distributive method

Distributive analysis was aimed at determining the possibilities of placement of locative components in the sentence. In Uzbek, the positional freedom of locative components is high, while in English their placement is limited by syntactic norms.

Moreover, one encounters cases where the distributive possibilities of a verb in a single form are different. It is also necessary to study the indicated cases of proportionality and disproportion. There may be a suspicion that the features of the distributive environment are related to the lexical meaning of the verb. Instead of a symbolic sign indicating which morphosyntactic group the word belongs to in the models given in it, it is necessary to define a specific verb. This makes it possible to divide verbs into different lexical-syntactic groups in relation to the commonality of their ability to combine.

When identifying these groups, the use of the substitution method is also important. The essence of this method is to change the position of different verbs in a circle.

In this way, additional clarifications are made to all forms of sentence structure. For example:

The Forbidden Forest held many creatures and mysteries (J.K. Rowling. Harry

Potter; 79)

The Forbidden Forest held many creatures and mysteries → Many creatures and mysteries were held in the Forbidden Forest → Where did hold many creatures and mysteries? → There\here held many creatures and mysteries

Distributive analysis provides complete information about the features of the interconnection of the parts of the syntactic series, but the analysis of sentence structure is not limited to the analysis of the main (core) part. The structure of a sentence is enriched and expanded due to non-nuclear, arbitrary elements.

Transformation method

With the help of the transformational method, sentences with a locative component were transformed into nominative and predicative constructions, and their hidden semantic possibilities were revealed.

The possibility of widespread use of the transformation method as a method of linguistic experiment to determine the syntactic-semantic features of sentence parts is shown by the analysis of the following examples:

The Great Hall was adorned with floating candles → There was adorned with floating candles. When comparing the sentences, we see that the part The Great Hall was adorned has an agentive meaning, and the second one does not have this distinguishing semantic feature. A.M. Mukhin advocates the use of the transformation method to distinguish the agentive syllable in the first sentence from the substantive syllable in the second:

He followed her, staying a few steps behind → She was followed by him, with a few steps kept between them.

In syntax, the transformation method is used for two main purposes:

1. for systematization (by determining the rules of "transition" of one sentence to another, we determine its place in the system of syntactic relations);
2. for classification (depending on the "action," "behavior" of parts of speech in the process of transformational changes, we determine and classify their syntactic-semantic functions).

Considering the difference between these two goals, when applying the transformation method, the processes of transformation synthesis and transformation analysis are activated. Of these, transformational analysis is activated by the purpose of classification, on the basis of which the systemic properties of language units are determined by replacing (changing) sentences and their constituent parts, and they are divided into designated groups.

Results. The research results showed the following:

1. In the Uzbek language, locativity is mainly expressed through morphological means.

2. In English, locative components are represented by prepositional combinations and have a syntactically stable position.

3. Locative components are an important unit that determines the semantics of a sentence in both languages.

4. Comparative analysis showed that locativity is a universal semantic category, but the methods of expression are specific to language.

Discussion. The obtained results show that a single grammatical approach to the analysis of sentences with a locative component is insufficient. The harmonious application of structural-semantic and cognitive methods helps to reveal the deep semantic layers of locative units. Differences in English and Uzbek serve as an important theoretical basis for translation, language teaching, and comparative linguistics.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the linguistic methods used in the analysis of sentences with a locative component allow us to comprehensively illuminate the semantics of the sentence. Comparative analysis, conducted on the example of the Uzbek and English languages, served to determine the general and national features of locativity.

In English and Uzbek, the locative allative sema is expressed through various syntactic structures. In English, it is mainly connected to verbs on the basis of a subordinative connection and is realized with the help of prepositional+noun combinations (into, to, towards, over to, etc.) and adverbs of place, while in Uzbek it is realized with the help of dative case suffixes (-ga, -qa, -ka) and additional units denoting place (ustiga, yoniga, qarshisiga, ichiga, etc.). In both languages, the locative allative sema indicates the direction of action, its implementation towards the object, and spatial delimitation. This shows that although the syntactic and semantic nature of the locative allative is universal, the means of its expression differ significantly depending on the typology of languages. At the same time, if in the Uzbek language the main means are suffixes and adverbial participles, then in the English language the role of prepositions is leading.

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